

Robot-based assessment and training of motor-cognitive dual-task abilities

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Abstract— People with neurological disorders and older adults often experience heightened mobility impairments, particularly in balance and gait, which are worsened during motor-cognitive dual-tasks. Research suggests that integrating motor and cognitive tasks can be a beneficial treatment. To date, there are few medical devices for motor-cognitive dual-task rehabilitation. Our long-term goal is to implement and integrate a new class of motor-cognitive dual-task exercises for training and assessment on the medical robot, *hunova*. As an interim step, this study focuses on the feasibility of a specific motor-cognitive dual-task: two unimpaired subjects performed the Trial Making Test while balancing on *hunova* in both static and dynamic conditions, while standing and sitting. The collected data allowed the computation of metrics that accurately measure subjects' motor and cognitive performance, also enabling the quantification of the decline in motor performance resulting from the inclusion of an additional cognitive task. Despite being in its preliminary stage, this study established the potential of dual-task exercises with *hunova*.

Keywords—motor-cognitive dual-task; neurological disorders; older adults; rehabilitation; robotic system, *hunova*.

I. INTRODUCTION

Aging, neurological disorders and brain injuries can lead to motor deficits [1], along with cognitive impairments, such as decreased information processing speed, reduced memory, attention-related issues and impaired executive functions [2]. The manifestation of these symptoms affects subjects' quality of life [3]. Many daily activities, as walking while talking on a cell phone or cooking while listening to a podcast, are examples of Motor-Cognitive Dual-Tasks (MCDT), as they consist in the simultaneous completion of cognitive and motor tasks.

Recent studies have shown that mobility impairments in multiple sclerosis, stroke, traumatic brain injuries, Parkinson's disease, and also in older adults are significantly exacerbated when performing MCDT [4]. This deterioration results from the reduced capacity of these subjects to divide their attention across multiple tasks simultaneously. Consequently, they need to recruit more cortical resources to achieve performance levels similar to those of young unimpaired adults [5].

In the past decade, research demonstrated that the mutual interference between motor and cognitive functions that occurs during dual-task conditions can be a beneficial treatment also for people with reduced motor abilities, as it improves coordination between two or even multiple tasks [6]. The importance of dual-task training gains additional emphasis from the understanding that deficits in executive function are linked to a higher risk of falls [7]. Also, dual-task training has been found to have positive effects on brain circuitry, not only for neuroplastic events, but also for the increased activation in prefrontal cortex [8]. This region is fundamental in executive functions, and facilitates the enhancement of the connectivity among brain regions involved in motor and cognitive processing [9]. Thus, MCDT training is now highly recommended in clinical use for different target populations.

In the last decades, many technological devices have been developed for the motor or cognitive assessments separately. There are only few devices that specifically target dual-task abilities, such as Bits Integrated Therapy System (BITS) by Bioness, and Dividat Senso (Dividat). However, none of these assess dual-task abilities in challenging situations, such as balancing in dynamic situations.

Within this context, we aim to integrate on *hunova* [10], a medical robotic device for the assessment and training of balance, trunk control and lower limbs, a new class of MCDT exercises. We begin by presenting a preliminary test on a first MCDT test, which assess balance while standing or sitting on both static or dynamic platforms and cognitive abilities. As cognitive assessment, we used the Trial Making Test (TMT), as it is widely used to measure spatial and visual research, attention skills, motor speed, working memory and mental flexibility. Currently, its most used version is the pen-and-paper format. However, we are proposing its digitalized version on *hunova* touchscreen to be performed while simultaneously maintaining balance.

II. PRELIMINARY STUDY

The goal of this preliminary test is to show the feasibility of a MCDT on *hunova*, which has two platforms, one under the feet and the other under the seat. Subjects were requested to perform both Single-Task (ST) and Dual-Task (DT) on *hunova* while standing in both static and dynamic conditions and while sitting in dynamic condition. In the static condition, the platform (foot platform while standing and seat platform while sitting) was maintained fixed, in the dynamic condition the platform was unstable, responding to the subject's postural sway. During the ST subjects were asked to remain as still as possible while fixating one single point on a wall. During DT, subjects were requested to remain as still as possible while completing the TMT on the device's touchscreen. We chose the TMT not only because it is one well-established cognitive assessment test, but also because it is easy to administer and is sensible in detecting possible cognitive damage [11]. TMT has two parts: part-A requires connecting numbers (1-25), and part-B requires switching between numbers and letters. In the pen-and-paper version, subjects' performance is scored based on the time taken to complete the exercises. Errors are recorded by the administrator without suspending the timing.

In this MCDT, the device provides information on both balance and cognitive performance. The former includes classical balance parameters such as measures of sway, temporal information of stabilization and quantification of trunk movements, computed using two force torque sensors under each platform and to the embedded inertial measurement units. For the purpose of this study, we present only *sway area*, which is computed as the 95% confidence ellipse area spanned by the center of pressure displacement. Moreover, to quantify the changes during the DT performance with respect to the ST, we computed Dual-Task Cost (DTC) defined as follows: $DTC = \left(\frac{DT-ST}{ST} \times 100 \right)$. To measure cognitive performance, we used the information related to the subjects' interaction with the touchscreen: the information of the finger position on the screen allows the computation of the classical parameters, such as *errors*: number of incorrectly reached targets and *test duration*: time taken to correctly connect the 25 targets, but also providing more specific information on the overall performance. Indeed, our version calculates also *execution time*: the actual drawing time, given by the sum of the time intervals during which the subjects' finger instant speed is above a threshold set to 10% of the maximum value of the filtered mean speed; *path precision*, as

Figure 1: Sway area of S1 and S2 is calculated for all three conditions for both Single-Task (ST) and Dual-Task (DT). Dual-task costs (DTC) for each subject in all configurations are also reported

Figure 2: Representative trajectory on hunova touchscreen

the accuracy with which the subject traces the path connecting the targets. In particular, for each target, the subjects' trajectory is compared with the ideal one. The global measure of precision is given by the mean value computed by the path precision on each pair of consecutive targets. For the purpose of this preliminary study, we tested two unimpaired subjects (S1: 25 years old female; S2: 29 years old female) to preliminary demonstrate the feasibility of MCDT exercises on hunova and provide preliminary evidence of the validity of the extracted performance parameters. In this study we present only the results for the TMT, part-A.

Results and discussions

Subjects successfully completed both ST and DT tasks in all three conditions. From a motor perspective, the sway area shows as S2 experienced a decline in motor performance during DT in all three conditions, while S1 worsened only in static-standing, and improved the motor performance in dynamic conditions (Fig.1). It is curious that both subjects showed the biggest worsening in performance in the DT compared to the ST in static conditions (as shown from the DTC in Fig.1).

Looking into details to the novel cognitive assessment Fig.2 shows an example of a subject's finger trajectory while performing the TMT on hunova's touchscreen. Concerning cognitive performance during DT, subjects completed the TMT test with no errors. S2 was faster in completing the test in standing (static test durations: S1: 86.4; S2: 67.5 s; dynamic test durations: S1: 64.4; S2: 62.8 s). Differently, for dynamic-sitting, the duration was comparable among subjects (S1: 61.1; S2: 61.8 s). The *execution time* and *path precision* showed as the two subjects used a completely different strategy in all three conditions. S1 had a bigger execution time (static-standing: S1: 43.1; S2: 29.6 s; dynamic-standing: S1: 46.1; S2: 27.5 s; dynamic-sitting: S1: 49.5; S2: 23.6 s) and less precise movements than S2 (static-standing: S1: 1.4; S2: 1.1 s, dynamic-standing: S1: 1.4; S2: 1.0 s, dynamic-sitting: S1: 1.3; S2: 1.0 s). These two results together explain the two different strategies used by subjects: S2 precisely moved only when knowing the

location of the next target, as S2 spent long time inside the targets, and likely scanned the screen for the next one before leaving the current one. Differently, S1 moved more and with less precise movements, as spent very little time inside the targets as was keeping moving while scanning the gaming area to locate the next target.

III. CONCLUSION

With this work, we presented a first version of a MCDT on hunova. This preliminary test supports the feasibility of DT exercises using this robotic device. We showed initial findings of a DT that required to stand and or sit, also in challenging situations, that included the TMT. We showed the changes in motor performance when adding also a cognitive task. Although we expected that the addition of a cognitive task would have led to worsening in motor performance, this was not true for S1 who performed better in the ST in dynamic conditions while both sitting and standing. For the first time, this study presents MCDT while balancing in unstable conditions by using a robotic platform. Although with two subjects we could not draw any conclusions, in future studies we aim to better understand how motor performance is affected when a cognitive task is added. Also, we deeply investigated the cognitive performance computing additional parameters that are normally not computed in the pen-and paper version. Indeed, the proposed digitalized version of the TMT offers several advantages: it guarantees a standardization of the test administration and scoring process, enhancing the reliability and validity of the test; by also providing more accurate and more meaningful results, enhancing the sensitivity and specificity of the test. Furthermore, future studies should also evaluate the changes in cognitive performance when adding a motor task. This is fundamental because it allows to understand task's prioritization.

In conclusion we presented the initial findings of a dual-task test, highlighting both motor and cognitive outcomes. Despite being preliminary, this study successfully showcased the viability of using MCDT on a medical robotic device. As a result, our objective is to expand the range of MCDT on hunova. Additionally, we aim to validate these exercises on a larger sample size, including both individuals without impairments and populations affected by neurological disorders, who could potentially benefit from MCDT training.

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DISCLAIMER

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REFERENCES

- [1] M. Amboni, P. Barone, and J. M. Hausdorff, "Cognitive contributions to gait and falls: Evidence and implications," *Mov. Disord.*, vol. 28, no. 11, pp. 1520–1533, 2013
- [2] L. P. De Andrade, et al. "Benefits of multimodal exercise intervention for postural control and frontal cognitive functions in individuals with Alzheimer's disease: A controlled trial," 2013,
- [3] R. Beurskens et al. "Age-related Deficits of dual-task walking: A review," *Neural Plast.* 2012
- [4] V. E. Kelly et al. "A review of dual-task walking deficits in people with Parkinson's disease: Motor and cognitive contributions, mechanisms, and clinical implications," vol. 2012
- [5] M. P. Boisgontier, et al. "Age-related differences in attentional cost associated with postural dual tasks: Increased recruitment of generic cognitive resources in older adults," 2013
- [6] N. Morelli et al. "The influence of cognitive tasks on sensory organization test performance," *Braz. J. Otorhinolaryngol.*, vol. 88, no. 6, pp. 841–849, 2021
- [7] F. C. Kearney et al. "The relationship between executive function and falls and gait abnormalities in older adults: A systematic review," *Dement. Geriatr. Cogn. Disord.*, vol. 36, no. 1–2, pp. 20–35, 2013
- [8] Park JH, "Effects of Cognitive-Physical Dual-Task Training on Executive Function and Activity in the Prefrontal Cortex of Older Adults with Mild Cognitive Impairment," 202
- [9] T. Wu et al. "Cerebellum and integration of neural networks in dual-task processing," *Neuroimage*, vol. 65, pp. 466–475, 2013
- [10] J. A. Saglia et al., "Design and development of a novel core, balance and lower limb rehabilitation robot: Hunova®," *IEEE Int. Conf. Rehabil. Robot.*, 2019
- [11] H. T. Kuo et al. "Effects of different dual task training on dual task walking and responding brain activation in older adults with mild cognitive impairment," *Sci. Rep.* 2022